

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

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About the Horizon 2020 project: ZeroPM – Zero Pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

ZeroPM, which stands for Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances, is a 5 year long, European research project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. ZeroPM interlinks three strategies to protect the environment and human health from persistent and mobile (PM) substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. Towards this, ZeroPM develops a framework guiding policy, technological and market incentives to minimize use, emissions and pollution of entire groups of PM substances.

The work package ‘Policy analysis, development, and assessment’ (Work Package 3) aims to contribute to the strengthening and enforcement of the EU chemicals policy framework in order to more effectively regulate persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances as well as incentivise and create an enabling environment for the uptake of alternative, sustainable chemicals. The second task (Task 3.2) in this work package aimed to identify regulatory opportunities and gaps in the existing policy/legal framework for preventing selected PMT/vPvM substances from entering the environment. The outputs of task 3.2 consist of three reports. The first one focuses on the Risk Management Option Analysis (RMOAs) of four PMT/vPvM substances; the second one focuses on EU strategies and action plans and the third one on discusses a potential approach for substance grouping of triazoles used as plant protection products, biocides and pharmaceuticals that degrade into 1,2,4-triazole.

Analysis of RMOAs of four PMT/vPvM substances

The first report looked at the RMOA of four substances – melamine (EC 203-615-4), 1,4-dioxane (EC 204-661-8), GenX (EC 799-974-4), and PFBS (799-977-0). These substances all meet PMT and/or vPvM hazard classes adopted in the CLP regulation (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008) as of December 2022. None of these RMOAs include the fact that the substances meet the PMT/vPvM hazard classes because the RMOAs were prepared before the hazard classes were adopted. Following their adoption, CLH proposals for classification as PMT and/or vPvM are currently in preparation for melamine and 1,4-dioxane. For the four substances, the RMOA has been carried out prior to the identification of the substances as substance of very high concern (SVHC) and recommended SVHC identification as a first step, based on Article 57(f) of the REACH Regulation (for substances raising an equivalent level of concern to other criteria set out in Article 57).

Results from the analysis of the RMOAs points to the fact that the main regulatory gap is the fact that PMT and vPvM hazard classes are not listed in Article 57 of the REACH Regulation as SVHC criteria. This complicates the identification of PMT/vPvM substances as SVHC as they must meet the conditions for application of Article 57(f) and present an equivalent level of concern compared to other SVHC criteria. Subsequently this limits possibilities for rapid regulatory action that follows the inclusion of a substance on the Candidate List. The amendment of Article 57 to add PMT, vPvM and endocrine disruptors in the list of SVHC criteria was included in the action plan of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic free Environment (CSS), adopted in 2020. Delays in the revision of REACH have postponed implementation of this action and the likelihood, timeline and content of a future revision of the REACH Regulation is still uncertain. The inclusion of PMT and vPvM hazard classes in Article 57 of the REACH Regulation constitutes an opportunity for adopting quicker regulatory action under the REACH Regulation (authorisation and restriction) and possibly outside the REACH Regulation, as identification as SVHC identification can trigger monitoring and/or control measures under other EU legislation.

Analysis of EU strategies and action plans

The second report reviewed EU strategies and action plans adopted under the European Green Deal and some additional strategies adopted prior to the European Green Deal to identify regulatory opportunities and gaps for the regulation of PMT and vPvM substances. The report identified many objectives and planned actions in the reviewed strategies and action plans related to circular economy, waste, textiles and paper and packaging. These are considered as opportunities for further addressing PMT/vPvM in those areas. Plastics, soil remediation, water and effluent treatment and electronic devices constitute other areas addressed in reviewed strategies and action plans that offer regulatory opportunities for PMT/vPvM substances. The report identified that cosmetics

and pharmaceuticals were only barely addressed in the reviewed strategies and action plans, which can be considered as a gap, based on the amount of PMT and vPvM substances that can be found within corresponding products.

An overview gaps and opportunities identified for PMT/vPvM substances is below:

Gaps:

- Delay of revising REACH Article 57 to add PMT and vPvM substances to the list of substances of very high concern,
- Lack of efficiency of authorization attempts related to products being imported into the EU,
- Lack of focus on better harmonization and substitution of chemicals,
- Lack of direct regulatory ambitions specifically targeting PMT/vPvM substances,
- Lack of EU focus on cosmetics and pharmaceuticals with respect to PMT/vPvM substances,
- Data and time constraints lead to short term regulatory action and insufficient long-term regulatory measures (related: slow international regulatory progress).

Opportunities:

- REACH and the Industrial Emissions Directive in terms of legal areas that may progress PMT/vPvM substance regulation,
- First steps for regulating PMT/vPvM substances include SVHC identification, and possibly restriction approaches dependent on time and data constraints,
- PFAS as a regulatory gateway for other PMT/vPvM substance groups,
- Textiles, plastic, paper and packaging as well as the chemical industry in terms of use and sectors that may progress PMT/vPvM substance regulation,
- Waste and circular economy approaches, especially in terms of recycling and the concentration of chemicals residing inside (contaminated) materials.

Regulatory gaps and opportunities for triazoles in biocides, plant protection products, and pharmaceuticals legislation

The third report investigated regulatory gaps and opportunities with a specific focus on 1,2,4-triazole-containing substances and explored the potential of substance grouping approaches for 1,2,4-triazoles. Triazoles are commonly used as plant protection products (fungicides and herbicides), biocidal products (wood preservatives), which have common transformation products (1,2,4-triazole, triazole acetic acid, and triazole

alanine). A few pharmaceutical products have also been identified as degrading into 1,2,4-triazole, however they are suspected not to have significant environmental release.

While 1,2,4-triazole has been detected in surface and groundwater in several EU Member States, the report identified that monitoring data is still limited. Although Germany and other EU member states have initiated monitoring efforts for 1,2,4-triazole in groundwater, such efforts are still scarce and incomplete. Expanding current monitoring programs, establishing new monitoring programs (particularly in high-exposure agricultural areas) and refining risk assessments based on new data would support better regulation of these substances.

Regarding biocides, the consideration in the environmental risk assessment is that the ecotoxicity of 1,2,4-triazole is lower than that of its parent compounds. This may lead to reduced attention during regulatory evaluations and could represent a potential gap as the cumulative effects of metabolites, which can originate from several biocides on the market, might not be comprehensively regulated. As substance properties regarding degradation and distribution behaviour should be considered in the environmental risk assessment, the application of the PMT and vPvM hazard classes could influence future risk assessments for triazoles. Regarding plant protection products, no general gaps in the regulatory framework was identified; however, some substance-specific gaps were identified. Although it should be assessed as a relevant metabolite (rM) due to its classification as reprotoxic 1B, 1,2,4-triazole has not been assessed for all triazoles (e.g. in the assessment of tebuconazole).

Documented evidence of significant release of 1,2,4-triazole or other triazoles from (human or veterinary) pharmaceuticals is unclear. However, some general considerations on the legal framework for pharmaceuticals can be made. The environmental risk assessment (ERA) tends to focus on the parent active substances, while metabolites and transformation products, including 1,2,4-triazole, are generally not taken into account in the ERA. Even if metabolites are identified in degradation tests, there are no regulatory consequences upon identification. This could potentially represent a regulatory gap.

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